

The Med-CORDEX phase 3 baseline runs : update after 1 year

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Med-CORDEX, phase 2 (2016-2022)

the 5 modelling pillars

BASELINE runs

Charact. past climate variability and future change, climate phenomena and impacts

RCSM 10-50 km
Atm-Land-River-Ocean

Evaluation 1979-2015 Scenario, 1971-2100
RCP8.5, RCP2.6

FMZ: free modelling zone

Push the limits of current protocols
Test new ideas

FPS convection

Convection phenomena at high-resolution over Europe and the Mediterranean

Convection-Permitting RCM 1-3 km
1°-17°E ; 40°-50°N

Case study Scenario RCP8.5
1996-2005
Evaluation 2000-2014 2041-2050 2090-2099

FPS air-sea

Role of the air-sea coupling and small-scale ocean processes on regional climate

Sensitivity tests to RCSM wave ORCM
baseline runs Ocean zoom

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RCP8.5, RCP2.6

FPS aerosol

Role of the natural and anthropogenic aerosols in the Mediterranean region

improved aerosol climatology interactive aerosol

Evaluation 1979-2015 Scenario, 1971-2100
RCP8.5, RCP2.6

The baseline runs can be seen as a continuation of phase 1 simulations

Med-CORDEX, phase 3 (2022-...)

the modelling pillars so far

BASELINE runs

High-resol. coupled climate simulations, focus on hazards and associated impacts

RCSM
Atm-Land-River-Ocean ~10 km

Evaluation	Scenario
ERA5 1979-2020	CMIP6, 1961-2100 SSP5-8.5, SSP1-2.6

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Evaluation	Scenario
1979-2015	1971-2100 RCP8.5, RCP2.6

The baseline runs can be seen as a logical continuation of phase 1 and 2 baseline runs

Phase 3 - Baseline runs :

main principles and objectives

- Built on the Med-CORDEX history ... the **coupled RCMs**, also called **RCSMs** or **RESMs**
- Develop **specific modelling framework** (based on the CORDEX-CMIP6 framework) to study the **Mediterranean climate** from multiple perspectives
- Create a **coordinated ensembles** of **coupled high-resolution climate simulations** to **fill identified research gaps**, e.g. highlighted by the IPCC-AR6 (WGI, WGII)
- Focus on the impact of global warming for different **hazards** in the Mediterranean basin at **several Global Warming Levels**: marine heatwave, severe storm including Medicanes, coastal erosion and flooding, coastal urban heat stress, mean and extreme sea level, dust outbreaks, compound hazards
- Serve the needs of the **impact community** to **assess the risks** for the marine and coastal ecosystems, the coastal urban areas, and the small island's environment, tourism, fluvial and marine transportation, fisheries and aquaculture, energy production

Baseline runs :

modelling framework / simulation protocol

- Built on the phase 1 and phase 2 Med-CORDEX experience with coupled simulations and on the **CORDEX-CMIP6** protocol
- Keep the **same Med-CORDEX minimal domain**: Med Sea, Black Sea and related catchment basins (except for the Nile)
- Use **fully-coupled RCSM** including, at least, **atmosphere, land, river** and **ocean** components
- Use **improved model versions** : coupled rivers, higher resolution (min. **12 km** mandatory for atm, min. **10 km** for ocean), new components accepted, improved present climate behaviour, sea level representation
- Share a **clear, open and well-documented simulation protocol** (zenodo, version : 29 sept 2022)
- Share **common ocean initial conditions and common forcings**: MedHYMAP, ERA5/ORAS5, CMIP6 GCMs, constant 12-values for the Nile, Chl-a dataset, evolving GHG, evolving aerosols
- Each proposed dataset has been tested and have a contact point for data access
- Share **common spin-up criteria**
- We do accept **new participating modelling groups** : IMS
- When relevant, « Phase 1 RCSM runs », « Phase 2 baseline runs » and « Phase 3 baseline runs » can be used together
- The « Free Modelling Zone » allows to test this protocol to propose improvements

Baseline runs : participation

- 11 potential participating modelling groups
- **4 models ready** : CNRM, ENEA, GUF, ICTP
- 4 models in development : IPSL, CMCC, UBEL, IMS
- 3 groups interested : LMD, AWI-GERICS, ITU
- Atm-RCMs : WRF, RegCM, ALADIN, COSMO, EBU
- Ocean-RCMs : NEMOMED, Nemo_MFS, Mitgcm, POM
- New components : natural and anthropogenic aerosols, waves, ocean biogeochemistry, human water use
- Please update regularly
- Please indicate the model reference article
- **Please be careful with model naming** → you change anything (resolution, physical parameterizations, tuning, new component), you change the name
- Model documentation : to be defined. not yet started. Any volunteer ?

*CLMcom-GUF-CCLM5-0-9-
NEMOMED12-3-6*

ICTP-RegCM-ES

CNRM-RCSM6

ENEA-REG

Baseline runs :

evaluation run status

- Minimal common period : 1979-2020
- Extension to past and recent periods welcome
- Runs completed for phase 3 : 1/11

Simulations done, Simulations in preparation

Model Naming	Period	Status	Last update
CNRM-RCSM6	1980-2022 then 1940-2022 when possible	planned	2023-04
ENEA-REG	1980-2014	done	2023-05
CLMcom-GUF-CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12-3-6	???	planned	2023-04
ICTP-OGS-RegCM-ES	1979-2020	planned, ocean model spin-up	2023-05
IPSL-RegIPSLv2	???	planned	2023-05
LMD-LMDZMED	???	interested	2023-05
CMCC-CCLM4-21-NEMOMFS (12km)	???	interested	2022-03
UBEL-EBUPOM2e	???	planned	2023-05
ITU-RegESMxxx	???	interested	2022-04
AWI-GERICS-ROM11xxx	???	interested	2022-03
IMS-ICON-OASIS-NEMO	???	planned	2023-04

Baseline runs : scenario run status

➤ Run status + GCM + Scen + Member:

- Minimal 1961-2100 (extension to 1950 recommended, to 1850 welcome)
- A total of ~20 simulations expected
- 4 scenarios with priority level: SSP370, SSP126, SSP585, SSP245
- 5 runs completed : GUF, ENEA, CNRM
- 3 driving GCMs so far: CNRM-ESM2-1, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, EC-Earth3-Veg

Please also fill
the CORDEX SAT
google document
with the eval
and scen run status

Simulations done, Simulations in preparation

Model	Driving GCM	Scenario, Period	Status	Last update
CNRM-RCSM6	CNRM-ESM2-1, r1i1p1f2	SSP585, 1979-2100	done	2023-04
CNRM-RCSM6	CNRM-ESM2-1, r1i1p1f2	SSP370, at least 1961-2100	planned	2023-04
CNRM-RCSM6	CNRM-ESM2-1, r1i1p1f2	SSP126, at least 1961-2100	planned	2023-04
CNRM-RCSM6	One or more GCMs to be chosen, probably among CMCC-CM2-SR5, NorESM2-MM	SSP370, at least 1961-2100	planned	2023-04
ENEA-REG	MPI-ESM1-2-HR r1i1p1f1	SSP585, 1979-2100	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG	MPI-ESM1-2-HR r1i1p1f1	SSP245, 1979-2100	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG	MPI-ESM1-2-HR r1i1p1f1	SSP126, 1979-2100	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG	MPI-ESM1-2-HR r1i1p1f1	SSP370, 1960-2100	planned	2023-05
ENEA-REG	EC-Earth3	SSP370, 1960-2100	planned	2023-05
CLMcom-GUF-CCLM5-0-9-NEMO MED12-3-6	EC-Earth3-Veg, r12i1p1f1	SSP585, 1950-2100	done	2023-04
ICTP-OGS-RegCM-ES	possible contribution with one or more GCMs among MPI-ESM1-2-HR, CNRM-ESM2-1, NorESM2-MM, EC-Earth3-Veg,	SSP370	planned	2023-05
ICTP-OGS-RegCM-ES	possible contribution with one or more GCMs among MPI-ESM1-2-HR, CNRM-ESM2-1, NorESM2-MM, EC-Earth3-Veg,	SSP126	planned	2023-05
IPSL-RegIPSLv2	IPSL-CM6A-LR, r???	SSPxxx, 1970-2100	Not sure	2023-05
LMD-LMDZMED			unknown	
CMCC-CCLM4-21-NEMOMFS (12km)			unknown	
UBEL-EBUPOM2e			unknown	
ITU-RegESM1.2			unknown	
AWI-GERICS-ROM11			unknown	
IMS-ICON-OASIS-NEMO			planned	

Baseline runs :

documentation, data sharing and scientific studies

➤ **Relevant documents are published on the Med-CORDEX community zenodo**

- Simulation protocol, output variable lists, model list, simulation lists
- Grey literature documents: task team rendering, forcing dataset description, model description and evaluation

➤ **Need to develop multi-model studies to increase robustness**

- We share runs for the mutual benefit of our personal scientific topics
- We share co-authorship for the key multi-model articles
- Many relevant scientific topics were not covered by Phase 1 and Phase 2 publications

➤ **New reference web page for Phase 3** : <https://www.medcordex.eu/simulations-phase3.php>

➤ **Need a new reference paper** after Ruti et al. 2015 (phase 1) and Somot et al. 2018 (phase 2)

➤ **A 2-stage data sharing procedure:**

- A central ftp for sharing inside the community
- ESGF publication for sharing outside the community

Phase 3 - Baseline runs :

Conclusions

- The initiative has really started (some models ready, first runs completed)
- Some reference documents missing: final protocol, ocean variable list, archive specifications
- Need for outcomes of the spin-up and GCM selection task teams
- Need for an internal sharing data repository
- Start raising the awareness in the targeted data user communities
- Need to define the model and run documentation strategy
- Funding is needed for some partners, a European project would be timely

BASELINE runs

High-resol. coupled climate simulations, focus on hazards and associated impacts

RCSM	~10 km
Atm-Land-River-Ocean	
Evaluation ERA5 1979-2020	Scenario CMIP6, 1961-2100 SSP5-8.5, SSP1-2.6

Model	Driving GCM	Scenario, Period	Status	Last update
CMRM-RCSM	CMRM-ESM2-1_r11p1f2	SSP585, 1979-2100	done	2023-04
CMRM-RCSM	CMRM-ESM2-1_r11p1f2	SSP202, at least 1961-2100	planned	2023-04
CMRM-RCSM	CMRM-ESM2-1_r11p1f2	SSP202, at least 1961-2100	planned	2023-04
CMRM-RCSM	One or more GCMs to be chosen, probably among CMIP6-ESM2-1, NorESM2-MR	SSP202, at least 1961-2100	planned	2023-04
ENEA-REG	MP-ESEM1-2-HR-r11p1f1	SSP585, 1979-2100	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG	MP-ESEM1-2-HR-r11p1f1	SSP245, 1979-2100	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG	MP-ESEM1-2-HR-r11p1f1	SSP202, 1979-2100	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG	MP-ESEM1-2-HR-r11p1f1	SSP202, 1960-2100	planned	2023-05
ENEA-REG	EC-Earth3	SSP202, 1960-2100	planned	2023-05
CLMsim-GUF-COLM3-S-NEMO-MIROC2-H	EC-Earth3-Veg_r12hp1f1	SSP585, 1960-2100	done	2023-04
ICTP-DOB-RegCM-EE	possible contribution with one or more GCMs among MP-ESEM1-2-HR, CMRM-ESM2-1, NorESM2-MR, EC-Earth3-Veg	SSP202	planned	2023-05
ICTP-DOB-RegCM-EE	possible contribution with one or more GCMs among MP-ESEM1-2-HR, CMRM-ESM2-1, NorESM2-MR, EC-Earth3-Veg	SSP202	planned	2023-05
IFU-RegCM1-d	IFU-CM4LR_????	SSPmax, 1979-2100	not sure	2023-05
LMU-UMGEM2			unknown	
CMCC-CO3M-21-ARNOVA's (10km)			unknown	
IRSL-ERLPO3km			unknown	
IFU-RegCM1-2			unknown	
AW-ORCS-ROCM1			unknown	
IMM-ICON-OASIS-MEMO			planned	